

The analysis of differentially expressed proteins to identify early biomarkers of disease progression in patients with seminoma

Vesna Ćorić^{a,b}

^aInstitute for medical and clinical biochemistry, Faculty of medicine University of Belgrade, Serbia

^bCenter for Redox medicine, Faculty of medicine University of Belgrade, Serbia

Introduction: The best course of action for patients with clinical stage I (CS I) seminoma is to manage them using a risk-adapted strategy, that includes surveillance when risk factors are absent, and adjuvant carboplatin-based chemotherapy, when risk factors are present. *Rete testis* invasion and a tumour diameter larger than 4 cm represent debatable prognostic factors. Reliable biomarkers stratifying the risk of relapse for CS I seminoma patients are urgently needed in order to routinely manage these patients using a risk-adapted strategy. Currently, no such biomarker is implemented into clinical recommendations or decision-making processes.

The aim: To compare the proteomic profile of formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) testicular cancer biopsies, of patients who relapsed with those who did not relapse within the 5-year period of active surveillance, in order to identify differentially expressed proteins.

Materials and methods: Protein extraction from 8 FFPE samples was performed with an SDS-based buffer following beads homogenization and boiling. Extracted proteins were analyzed by GeLC-MS/MS followed by statistical and bioinformatics analysis.

Results: Statistically significant difference in expression was obtained for three proteins (PFN1, CSTA, PRSS3). Namely, PRSS3, CSTA and PFN1 were up-regulated in patients who relapsed.

Conclusion: The expression level of certain proteins may reflect prognosis in CS I seminoma patients. Validation of the preliminary proteomics findings by method of immunohistochemistry in an independent patient cohort will allow assessment of the clinical utility of the putative biomarkers. Further analysis, controlling for clinical confounders is also required for better risk assessment.

Corresponding Author: Vesna Ćorić

Institute for medical and clinical biochemistry, Faculty of medicine University of Belgrade, Serbia

Center for Redox medicine, Faculty of medicine University of Belgrade, Serbia

2 Pasterova Street, Belgrade, Serbia

drcoricvesna@gmail.com

+381 11 2643272